

An integrated robotically-driven workflow for the development of elastic tensile structures in various scales

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This paper presents an ongoing work towards the development of an integrated robotically-driven workflow that can be used for the design, development and subsequent fabrication of small-to large-scale elastic tensile mesh structures. This approach involves digital form-finding and optimization, driven by robotic manufacturing principles and it aims to overcome the limitations of currently available tools, to work either in the design or the fabrication phase of the process. At the same time, it involves the fabrication of systems in several scales followed by respective analyses of results according to the specific type and diameter of the material used. Specifically, form-finding and optimization are responsible for controlling the pretension of the elastic threads, aiming to determine the final tensile mesh and to generate the additive robotic tool-path. In parallel, the type and diameter of the material involved, define the necessary changes of the end-effector tool, which is responsible to implement the process. Despite that design results can be in any scale, for study purposes an experimentation into a small-scale is conducted, to evaluate the suggested automated construction process in general and the end-effector mechanism in particular.

Keywords: *Tensile structure, elastic material, optimization, robotically-driven workflow, robotic fabrication*

INTRODUCTION

The knowledge in regard to the design and fabrication of tensile mesh systems requires an in-depth investigation of their geometric, static and construction complexity. Similar information can be derived from natural mechanisms such as silk, spider weave and soap films. The study of such mechanisms through physical experimentation and digital simulation enables a deeper understanding of their form and structural behaviour. Nevertheless, a com-

prehensive integration of these results within a design and fabrication workflow requires the development of innovative design tools and digital fabrication mechanisms (Duro-Royo et al, 2015). In order to achieve structural efficiency as well as accuracy and precision regarding the physical results obtained, new directions of research require a more interactive relationship between design and fabrication.

Initial ideas trace back to the work of Frei Otto

in the Stuttgart Institute of Lightweight Structures, where soap films or other materials were used for physical form-finding (Otto et al, 2006). The gradual introduction of digital tools for form-finding and, in parallel, the ability to simulate the behaviour of any material (Gramazio and Kohler, 2008) allow progressive integration of manufacturing processes within this area of research. A principal factor in this procedure is the material deformation behaviour, which varies according to the changes occurring during fabrication. Another issue that is taken into account is the scale of production that varies and depends on the ability of the mechanisms provided.

As regards the digital design and static analysis part of the process, techniques might range from form-finding to spring-based simulation, sometimes integrated with optimization techniques, for instance by applying Genetic Algorithms (GA). As regards the fabrication workflow, the continued development of automated construction techniques open new directions that move beyond a conventional physical form-finding method towards an automated procedure that might include and/or combine design and construction experimentation (Keating and Oxman, 2013). The use of industrial robots, aerial robots or gantries improves the control of the process, allowing, in parallel, an easy scale up or scale down of the structural systems under production. In addition, the advanced kinematic flexibility of mechanisms leads to a number of advantages as compared to conventional approaches, such as the safety of workers and the control accuracy of materials.

All the above lead to the development of integrated digital design to fabrication techniques that might include user-friendly interfaces for design exploration, which combine real-time form-finding methods, structural optimization control and robotic simulation (Braumann and Brell-Cokcan, 2012), together with techniques that enable the construction of innovative materials in a wide range of scales. Related works in this direction can be found, for instance in the experimental investigation undertaken in (Wendy and Antoine, 2016), where semi-

autonomous wall-based robots are developed for the weaving of a small installation with carbon threads. The main advantage of this example is that it enables the materialization of new structures that would be impossible to build by employing normal fabrication strategies. Based on similar material principles, in the example of (Knippers et al, 2012), a custom-made tool is developed and mounted on the robotic arm for controlling and feeding with thread material. By applying robotic simulation, form-finding and structural performance analysis, the construction of the overall structure can be effectively achieved. The simulation of robotic movement behaviour, the tool-path generation and the structural performance allow the adjustment of robotically-driven workflows in real scale structures.

SUGGESTED METHODOLOGY

The integration of form-finding, structural optimization and robotic fabrication principles is in the forefront of the current research study, which aims to investigate the ability of the proposed workflow to achieve robust results in terms of their shape, static behaviour as well as constructability. Within this framework, this work focuses on the development of a parametrically controlled algorithm that can be used for the manufacturing of elastic tensile structures in various scales. The aim is to optimize the elastic tensile behaviour and hence the robotic tool-path in order to achieve an automated fabrication process that can respond to different needs. This is achieved through the involvement of several parameters and criteria that include material characteristics such as elasticity and diameter, additive weaving techniques as well as design decisions, affecting the end results of mesh structures.

The suggested algorithm is developed in the parametric design environment of Grasshopper [1], a plug-in for Rhino software [2], aiming to formulate the three-dimensional input surface and to control the initial curvature, the surface division and the scale, which influence the mesh configuration. The process of form-finding is achieved using the physics-

based software Kangaroo (Piker, 2013), a plug-in for Grasshopper. The static equation aims to simulate the non-linear mesh behaviour (Figure 1). An important aspect of elastic mesh system development is the balance occurring between the material pretension and tensile strength that prevents the establishment of high sag threads geometry. The relaxation process of threads is achieved in digital environment using spring behaviour. The springs strength is described by the mathematical equation $K = \frac{A \cdot E}{L}$, where K is the spring stiffness, A is the cross-sectional area, E is the (tensile) elastic modulus of the rubber (Polyurethane Elastomer) thread (0.02 GPa) and L is the length of the thread. Thus, during the simulation process, pretension forces are applied on threads that cause overall deformation and stabilisation of grid structure. In parallel, using the general-purpose civil-engineering software SAP2000 [3] the form-finding results are evaluated and correlations with the parametric ones are derived.

Figure 1
Final weaving
pattern applied in
real scale
case-study B.8

The complexity of parameters and material limitations lead to the introduction and development of a multi-objective optimization analysis process based on MOGA (Deb, 2002). The optimization process controls the material section and the pre-stress be-

haviour as well as the construction parameters such as dimension of nodes and positioning (Kilian and Ochsendorf, 2005). The results are based on the material tensile strength (5MPa) and the parameters of end-effector tool that enable the handling of the additive process using an industrial robotic arm (Kontovourkis and Tryfonos, 2016). Through the simulation, a population of best solutions is generated. The Pareto front suggests a series of best solutions followed by the selection of desirable ones based on their ease of robotic fabrication, on their static behaviour under external load and on their initial morphology.

The suggested automated fabrication workflow (Figure 2) aims to generate a weaving tool-path that is responsible for the progressive addition of material, leading to the deformation of the overall mesh. In order to evaluate the results of digital optimization workflow and to observe the effect of robotic fabrication within the framework of an actual construction procedure, the proposed scenario is implemented using small-scale physical prototypes. In this paper, the aim is to investigate different surface categories of the best tensile mesh solutions through the design of eight case-studies with different Gaussian curvatures. Within this framework, studies regarding the pre-stress of elastic threads and the topology of the nodes are also undertaken. The purpose of this investigation is to evaluate and correlate the solutions in each category as well as their case studies, based on structural performance criteria and fabrication constrains, allowing an automated mesh weaving process through the industrial robotic arm ABB IRB2600. Some important aspects for the typological development of the elastic threads are the limitations of the custom-made end-effector tool to effectively handle the rubber (Polyurethane Elastomer) thread of $\varnothing 0.8\text{mm}$. As the continuous motion of the robotic arm determines the initial morphology of the nodes and threads, the simulation, the analysis and the multi-objective optimization of the morphology control the pre-tension that influence robotic fabrication.

Figure 2
Diagram of the robotically-driven optimization workflow

GEOMETRICAL CONFIGURATION AND FORM-FINDING

In detail, the research explores eight different input categories with different Gaussian curvatures in the weaving algorithm. The geometric development of the categories for each elastic mesh is determined by the gradual change of two basic lines A and B at a distance (y). In parallel, changes of tree control points in lines (start, middle and end) in z-axis for each category results in eight surface variations with the two combined curves. The categories are developed base on 1x1 YZ coordinate system, allowing the easy scale down or scale up in any direction. Aim is to investigate the behaviour of the elastic mesh weaving algorithm by correlating the initial Gaussian curvature (Ks) and the final mesh Gaussian curvature (Kf) values. The Figure 3 shows the nine interior points of which the initial and final Gaussian curvature are measured.

Categories of weaving patterns

The category A shows the same transformation of A and B curves in the midpoint with value 0-0.7m. Each change occurs by increasing the position of mid-points by 0.1 meter and this creates the surface cases (A.1) to (A.8). Similarly, in category B, the changes occur simultaneously in both curve mid and end points. The midpoints are moved with the sequence (B.1) = 0, (B.2) = 0.05m and (B.3) - (B.8) = 0.1m by changing the parameter at the end points of the curves with an increase of 0.1m per case from (B.1) = 0 to (B.8) = 0.8m. Through those changes, it is observed that in all eight cases in categories A and B, the surface Gaus-

sian curvature (Ks) is zero. Thus, this is the result of the equation $K_s = \frac{1}{R1} \cdot \frac{1}{R2}$ where $R2 = \infty$ (Block et al, 2014).

Figure 3
Gaussian curvature measuring points

In categories C the change occurs in the curve B, where the midpoint moves to 0.1m in case (C.2) and remains constant in cases (C.2 to C.8) = 0.1m. Alongside, the endpoint changes 0.1m per case with maximum value 0.8m in case C.8. The changes in each case causes a gradual increase of surface Gaussian curvature with a maximum Ks = -1.24 unit at case C.8 point 8. Similarly, in category D the changes occur only in curve B, with the midpoint varied 0.1m per case from (D.1) to (D.8) with a maximum value 0.7m. Those transformations cause symmetrical changes in

Figure 4
Wave sequence of
the elastic thread

surface curvature, with points 0 and 6, 1 and 7 to have the same value, point 3,4,5 to have zero value and point 2 and 8 maximum value in case (D.8) with $K_s = -1,77$ units. The typology E has similar parameters with categories C and D to affect only curve B. The transformation occurs at the mid and end points of the curve B. In case (E.2) the mid and the end point have initial values 0.1m and 0.2m and this is increased at 0.1 per case (E.3) to (E.8) with maximum value 0.7m and 0.8m respectively. The movement of the points causes a maximum change of surface curvature $K_s = -1.46$ units at point 2 and the minimum change at points 6,7,8 with K_s value -0.3 to -0.5 units. The category F shows changes at both curves. In this case, the change occurs simultaneously at start and end point of curve A and at the midpoint of curve B. In case (F.2) the value sets at 0.2m and from (F.3) to (F.8) is increased by 0.1m per case with the maximum value of 0.8m. Consequently, surface Gaussian curvature changes in points 0,2,6,8 and 1,7 record the same value. Maximum value can be found at points 0,2,6,8 with $K_s = -2,79$ units, at points 1,7 with $K_s = -12,68$ units and at points 3,4,5 with fixed $K_a = 0$.

Category G applies same transformation principals with categories C at both curves A and B. In curves A and B midpoint is moved with the sequence (G.1) = 0, (G.2) = 0.05m and (G.3) - (B.8) = 0.1m. The curve A start point and curve B end point are increased by 0.1m per case from (G.1) = 0 to (G.8) = 0.8m. Therefore, the same value of Gaussian curvature is observed at points 0 and 8, 2 and 6, 1 and 7, 3 and 5, with a maximum curvature value $K_s = -1,32$, $K_s = -1,46$, $K_s = 2,01$, $K_s = -1,92$ units respectively and with maximum value at point 4 to be $K_s = -3,02$ units. Based on the results of case (G.8), in category H, curve's B midpoint from 0.1 value at (H.1) to 0.8 at (H.8) are increased. In result of the transformation, the surface Gaussian curvature maximum value shifts from point 4 to point 1 and 2, where at (H.8) is observe a maximum value of $K_a = -7,92$ and $K_a = -6,35$ units respectively. The table 1 shows the Z-axis movement of point in the curve A and B and the initial surface Gaussian curvature values.

Weaving development process

The simulation of the weaving algorithm aims to investigate the physical behaviour of the rubber elastic mesh for every surface variation of each category, testing in parallel the ability of the workflow to define the nodes sequence for the robotic toolpath generation. Furthermore, the parameters controlling the initial geometry can define the size of the surface and the weaving pattern density, the (div) that is the surface division in x and y direction, influencing the pattern density, the space (y) that is the distance between curves defining the surface and the value (x)

that is the distance of start to end point of each curve. This, in the small scale models for the robot working area, is $(div) = 1$ of total of 1 pattern unit, $y = x = 0.7$ m and for a full scale model $(div) = 6$ of total 36 unit patterns, $y = x = 4$ m. In detail, the 2 lines are divided by the parameter (N) in 9 or 11 or 13 equal nodes that are connected in one direction with the weaving sequence A3, B3, B5, A5, A7, B7, B9, A9, A11 and B11 creating springs 1-9. Then, B11 is connected with D1 with an additional spring. The weaving sequence continues in the other direction from D1 to C2 and intersects and divides any existing spring into two segments. Then, the process is repeated with the sequence C2, D3, C4, D5, C6, D7, C8, D9, C10 and D11, leading to the creation of spring between two nodes. In addition, the notes can be moved separately in the curve by 25-75% of the neighboring unconnected points. The remaining unconnected points on A, B, C and D curve are the connecting nodes to the adjacent units and/or to the anchor points leading to the results that represents the initial geometry of the ten-

sile mesh system in Kangaroo plug-in (Figure 4).

Physics-based simulation for form-finding

Initial investigation on the material deformation and the tensile forces, which are applied in the elastic thread have been determined in previous research (Kontovourkis and Tryfonos, 2016). The prestress is calculated based on the robot end-effector capability to apply accurately holding force in the thread during the prestress and the node creation process. This parameter is described by the thread length and the initial point distance (L/D) and is set at lower value of 70% for maximum deformation and at maximum value of 100% without deformation. Therefore, the change of (L/D) factor intends to set the prestress in the overall elastic mesh structure in order to avoid thread sags. Thus, based on the surface Gaussian curvature (K_s) results, where the anchorages-nodes can be moved from 25-75% affecting the mesh typology and curvature, the aim of this investigation is to further control tensile stress behaviour.

Categories		A			B			C			D		
Curves		A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B		
C (m)	Start	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
	Mid.	0-0.7	0-0.7	0-0.1	0-0.1	0	0-0.1	0	0-0.1	0	0-0.7		
	End	0	0	0-0.8	0-0.8	0	0-0.8	0	0-0.8	0	0		
Black = A curve Red = B curve													
(-)Ks		0	0	0	0	0	0	0.15	0.85	1.24	1.77	0	1.77
		0	0	0	0	0	0	0.09	0.6	1.09	0.75	0	0.75
		0	0	0	0	0	0	0.05	0.33	0.66	0.30	0	0.30
Categories		E			F			G			H		
Curves		B			A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	
C (m)	C (m)	0	0	0-0.8	0	0	0-0.8	0	0-0.8	0	0	0.8	
	Μέσο	0	0-0.7	0	0-0.8	0-0.1	0-0.1	0-0.1	0-0.1	0.1	0.1-0.8		
	Τέλος	0	0-0.8	0-0.8	0	0-0.8	0	0-0.8	0	0.8	0		
Black = A curve Red = B curve													
(-)Ks		1.46	0.44	0.05	2.79	0	2.79	1.46	1.92	1.32	7.92	1.18	0.07
		0.81	0.24	0.03	12.68	0	12.68	2.01	3.02	2.01	6.38	1.18	0.07
		0.44	0.14	0.02	2.79	0	2.79	1.32	1.92	1.46	1.56	0.82	0.07

Table 1
The initial surface
Gaussian curvature
for the 8 categories

The simulation is accomplished using the particle-spring behaviour modelling in Kangaroo plug-in for Grasshopper. To verify the process for the deformation results, the SAP2000 software is used. The material has high tensile strength ($F_t = 5\text{MPa}$) and yield stress ($F_y = 3\text{MPa}$) compared to the elastic module ($E = 2\text{MPa}$) and its Poisson's ratio is set to 0.5. All material characteristics are used as tendons inputs in the software. Therefore, the threads are simulated as cables with diameter 0.8mm with deformation prestress and self-weight of $\rho = 0.93\text{ Mg/m}^3$ (Ashby, 2011). Also, the node mass is calculated as point load with value -0.012985N . The SAP2000 nonlinear analysis shows that the Kangaroo form finding have 0.1mm - 0.6mm deviations that can be used for the elastic mesh simulation. Subsequently, in case of scale changes, the algorithm allows input thread diameter range from 0.8mm to 20mm and this enables setting of external loads.

OPTIMIZATION PROCESS AND RESULTS

The use of multi-objective optimization process via genetic algorithms (MOGA) allows handling of several multiple criteria and parameters leading to a range of acceptable and close to the optimum results. For optimization purposes, the Octopus optimization engine (Vierlinger and Bollinger, 2014) (plug-in for Grasshopper) is applied. The continuous alternation of the anchorages from 25%-75%, thread diameter 0.8 - 20mm and the length factor L/D 70-100% of mesh are simulated in Kangaroo plug-in, developing a population of acceptable solutions associated with the tensile stress, the amount of material used, the total deformation material and the allowed material tensile strength (F_a). This is based in the mathematical equation $F_a = \frac{F_{st} \cdot A}{S.F}$ (A = section area, $S.F$ = safety factor = 1.35) (Stranghöner et al, 2016). Also, simulation is associated with the material external load (1kN/m^2) and the capabilities of the custom-made end-effector tool. The selection of best solutions based on their tensile performance behaviour, the material deformation under external

load and the length of threads are achieved using the Pareto front (Pareto optimality). In case of the small scales experiments, the external load is set to zero and consequently the deformation under load is always zero. Therefore, the small-scale case studies locked the thread diameter parameters for the optimization process, since the diameter of available material is 0.8Ø .

The best results formulate the population of 100 solutions in each generation for 500 generations and are evaluated based on the reduction of the average tensile force, the reduction of material deformation under external load (small-scale case studies = 0) and the total length of the deformed threads. The deformation of threads, the length amount of threads required, the tensile forces and the curvature are the criteria to evaluate the static performance and constructability of structure in each case through 500 generations. By the application of multi-objective optimization process a range of possible results are produced. These are distinguished in two categories of optimum results based on their: a. Static behaviour by prioritizing tension and thread deformation changes, b. Geometrical configuration by prioritizing curvature changes.

Figure 5 shows the best trade-offs for generation 0,50,100,250 and 500 in the case (F.8). The graph describes the relationship between the average of the tensile stress and the length of the deformed thread, where in the 500th generation the best Pareto curve appears. The results shown that the solution (a) with the minimum tensile stress average 0.2649KN has the higher L/D factor = 73.22%, lower section diameter 0.9mm and deformation length material with value 415.8378m , with material length 282.2888m . In this case, the thread deformation under external load is maximum at 7.5106m , showing that this solution is the less statically acceptable with high node displacements and the most geometrically preferable with the lower final curvature (K_f) = -0.3098 . Alternatively, the solution (d) with the maximum tensile stress average 110.9773KN has the lowest L/D factor = 70%. higher section diameter 16.96mm and

Solutions	a	b	c	d
L/D(%)	73.22%	71.01%	70.23%	70%
Diameter (mm)	0.9	1.33	2.3	16.96
Average Tension(N)	0.2906	0.6961	2.0484	110.9773
Total Material Used (m)	282.2888	269.5728	269.5709	269.5726
Total material loaded deformation (m)	7.5106	1.3724	0.1905	0.0010
Average final curvature $-(K_f)$	0.3098	0.3177	0.3208	0.3216
$K = (-K_i) - (-K_f)$	-0.1064	-0.1143	-0.1174	-0.1182

Table 2
Results of case study F.8

the lowers deformation length material with value 409.9157m, with material length 269.5726m. In this solution, the thread deformation under external load is the minimum at 0.0010m. The static systems with the highest average tensile stress compared to systems with less average tensile stress can be considered optimum (Bechthold, 2008) for their static behavior, showing that this solutions are the most statically preferable with the less material length used. However, the maximum average final curvature and the higher section diameter makes this solution the less geometrical acceptable and this will require high pretension from the robotic system.

Since all cases are characterized as statically balanced and are retaining the construction parameters of the custom-made end-effector tool and the robotic setup, is decided to select and fabricate solutions that are away from the boundaries and near the center. Thus, acceptable solutions with less material length and better static behaviour are those that approach the maximum allowable (L/D) factor and show a higher average tensile stress and less material deformation under external load (Table 2, solution c). On the contrary, a system with a lower average tensile stress (Table 2, solution b) and a higher (L/D) factor shows less thread deformation, increasing the length of material need and displays more thread deformation under external load. Therefore, the solution (b) considered geometrically acceptable by showing less curvature changes than the original surface.

Figure 5
Results of population of solutions through the optimization process for case study F.8

Through the comparison of case studies in regard to the best geometrical configuration solutions, it is observed that case study A.7 hat the highest average tension with value 7.3471N and C.8 the lowest tension at value 0.375N. Proportionally, the material section diameter is higheest at case A.7 with 5.59mm and lowest at case study C.8 = 0.87mm. Subsequently, case study A.8 has the highest section diameter and the deformation that is caused by external load is the lowest at 0.2650m. Also, case study C.8 has the highest deformation thread under external load with value 6.7018m. Because of the propor-

tional relation, case study A.8 has the highest material in use 316.7124m and the highest Caucasian curvature change $K=-0.1722$. In opposite, case study C.8 has the lowest material in use 233.5152m and lowest curvature change $K=0.0019$. Since category G applies same transformation principals such as categories C, archives to decrease the curvature change at $K=0.0009$ by having the lowers initial prestress $L/D=85.98\%$. Due to this, category G has the optimum geometrically configuration category.

By comparing the best static behaviour solutions, it is observed that case A.7 has highest average tension 20.7863N and case study D.8 the lowest average tension at 0.5155N. Correspondingly, the material section diameter and material used is the highest at case study A.7 with 9.5m and at value 319.6323m respectively. In the other hand, the most economic material categories can be found in case study E.8 that has the lowest section diameter with value 1.3m and in case study C.8 that has the lowest material used with value 233.6752. Comparing the lowest thread deformation under external load, case study A.7 is the optimum static behaviour category.

In conclusion, solutions with high section diameter and high average tension have low deformation material under load and high curvature change and are considered to have better static behaviour. In opposite, solution with higher material deformation, lower average tension and section diameter have lower curvature change and are considered better in terms of their geometrical configuration.

Physical prototyping

The use of multi-objective optimization process via genetic algorithms (MOGA), the continues simulation of the custom-made end-effector tool and the robotic setup (ABB IRB 2600) with the structural behaviour of the elastic mesh allow the selection of the best form-finding solutions. In parallel, continuous refinement of tool path is required due to the deformation of the whole system in each new addition of thread and nodes. The redefinition of the tool path and hence the robotic manufacturing of

the final elastic mesh is achieved through the thread by thread progressive simulation of tensile's nodes addition. Preliminary experiments (Figure 6) show that the weaving algorithm and the simulation of the form-finding process can generate a robotic tool-path. In order to achieve high precision of physical models, calibration of the anchor points in the physical and digital model is required. Furthermore, future experiments will aim at the construction of small-scale structures that will fully represent the digital form-finding elastic mesh.

Figure 6
Preliminary
experiment on the
robotic
construction of an
elastic mesh
structure
(Kontovourkis and
Tryfonos, 2016)

CONCLUSION

This paper aims to demonstrate an integrated robotically-driven workflow from small- to large-scale development of elastic tensile mesh structures. Through an analytical investigation, the proposed robotically-driven optimization and fabrication workflow intends to examine the effectiveness of the process to be implemented in various scales using a specific automated construction procedure. The workflow is evaluated against its ability to con-

trol the initial design and the suggested form-finding process in an integrated manner, allowing at the same time, an automated weaving technique of manufacturing to occur. Further work will continue towards the physical realization of the results derived from form-finding, simulation and analysis workflow. Also, comparative studies that examine models in digital and physical environment will be developed.

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